

Role of National Constituency Development Fund in Enhancing Access to Public Secondary School Education in Mombasa County

Author's Details:

Beatrice W. Kadori^{a*} Mr. Benjamin M. Mwawasi^b Mr. Paul Mwenda^c

^{ab}School of Education and Social Sciences ^cSchool of Business and Economics, Kenya Methodist University

Abstract

The issue of financing education, especially secondary education is a growing concern in the Kenyan education system. The government through the Ministry of Education (MoE) has employed financing strategies such as bursaries for the needy but bright students through National Constituency Development Fund (NCDF). The purpose of this study was to assess the role of National Constituency Development Fund (CDF) in enhancing access to secondary school education in Mombasa County. The study objectives were to; assess the role of NCDF of improving access rate in enhancing access to secondary school education in Mombasa County, examine the role of NCDF in provision of infrastructural facilities in enhancing access to secondary school education in Mombasa County and to assess role of NCDF in provision of instructional resources in enhancing access to secondary school education in Mombasa County. The study was based on Decentralization and economic Theory. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The target populations for the study was 32 public secondary schools in Mombasa County (15 schools in Mvita, 6 schools in Likoni, 6 schools in Chagamwe and 5 schools in Kisauni Sub-Counties), 32 principals and 582 teachers from the schools in the four Sub-Counties totaling to 646 people. The results were analyzed by the application of descriptive statistics and presented in percentages, means, frequency distribution tables, and pie charts. The expected outcome of the study was the determination of the role of NCDF in enhancing access to secondary school education and other methods used to finance secondary education in Mombasa County. This study research found that NCDF has a role in enhancing access to public secondary school education in Mombasa County. Aspects of NCDF that enhance access to public secondary school education in Mombasa County included Improving Access Rate, Provision of Infrastructure Facilities and Provision of Instructional Resources. The study recommends that as much as possible CDF bursary awarded to students should be adequate to sustain the students in schools and improve their survival rates. The government should increase the amount of CDF dispatched to schools for improvement and growth of school infrastructure so as to enhance access to secondary education. School administrators should encourage needy students to apply for bursaries and help them access the fund. In the same way, they should make an effort to get the fund for infrastructure development in their schools. Further, this research study recommends further studies in other counties other than Mombasa so as to make a comparison.

Keywords: Constituency development fund, Access, Infrastructure facilities, Instructional resources

1.0 Introduction

It is generally observed that governments in the world spend significant resources in education and this has led to a tremendous expansion of education opportunities although the level of challenges for many youths especially from the poor backgrounds have not been reduced (Patrinos, 2001). According to Mosoti (2015) education is the main equalizer of the gapping inequalities in modern life, more so on the socio-economic facet. Adeyeni and Adu (2010) state that education is one of the leading instruments for promoting economic development as it encompasses some processes individuals goes through to help them develop in utilizing their potentials. World Bank (2011) attests that demand for secondary education is soaring due to progress towards universal primary education. However, the heightened demand for education is accompanied by the need to respond to the twin challenges of increasing access to and at the same time improving quality and relevance of secondary education in an environment where the national budgets are already constrained. Woodhall (2004) indicates that many countries affiliated to World Bank especially in Latin America and East Asia have shown an increasing interest in expanding and strengthening their secondary education systems despite challenges such

as lower completion rates for young people from lower income levels. In Chile, municipal schools receive financing for infrastructure such as classrooms, playgrounds and also for operating costs from the government so as to expand schools which increased participation of the student in learning (Patrinos and Sosale, 2011). In Uganda, the Government aided community schools by giving capitation and development grants to improve school programmes and infrastructure.

In Kenya, an historical analysis of the patterns and trends of education financing reveals the existence of a partnership between the state, households, and communities, long before the introduction of the cost-sharing policy by the Government of Kenya as cited by Orodho (2005). To show commitment to ensure increased access to basic education, the Government of Kenya through Kenya Secondary School Bursary Programme awards financial support to poor and vulnerable children who cannot get alternative support to finance their secondary school education (Ngware, Onsomu, and Muthaka, (2007). Monchari (2004) opines that bursary subsidies at the national level were not meeting the access and participation levels in secondary schools and the needy had not kept pace as it was expected. According to Ayodo (2006), the rising costs of living have made many students from poor families fail to access to and drop out of their secondary school education. Even with the subsidised secondary school education in Kenya from 2008, the operational costs of secondary schools have remained high with an average cost of boarding secondary schools at Kshs. 30,000 and day schools at Kshs. 10,000 per year is still not affordable to many Kenyans (Ayodo). Based on these challenges facing bursary management, the Government of Kenya initiated the Constituency Development Fund (CDF as it was called by then) in 2003 with the objective of assisting the poor and vulnerable groups in the community (the Republic of Kenya, 2002).

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Despite the National Constituency Development Fund being helpful to the needy children, many research findings have dismissed it. For instance, Obiero (2014) found out that nepotism and corruption posed a challenge to the allocation of CDF bursary to needy students. On the same note Ngalu and Bomett, (2014) note that lack of information on when to apply for CDF bursary, inadequate amount awarded were challenges facing CDF bursary for secondary schools in Kilome Constituency while Obwari (2013) asserts that the CDF funds were not enough and as a result many students are sent home or waste a lot of time looking for the funds. Since 2003 the GOK allocates bursary and school subsidy either directly or through NCDF. The main aim is to enhance access to secondary school education and provide infrastructural support in public secondary schools (Obiero, 2014). It is expected that school bursary from the NCDF will enhance access rate in secondary school education being in support of the government's policy on the provision of compulsory secondary education at the grassroots level. According to the first Mombasa County Development Plan (CIDP) 2013-2017, the Mombasa county government has continuously endeavored to improve the basic educational infrastructure such as classrooms and other school facilities.

In most Counties in Kenya, there are allegations that the administrative system of CDF faces inefficiency and irregularities such as delays in disbursement of funds, corruption, political patronage and nepotism. Worse still is lack of defined eligibility criterion, inadequate awareness of the NCDF bursary funds (Obiero, 2014). According to Njeru and Orodho (2003), the NCDF subsidies are not equitably distributed to the recipients and that the students from poor urban families are still unable to access secondary school education despite the availability of the NCDF. To this effect, the study aimed to assess the role of NCDF in enhancing access to public secondary school education in Mombasa County.

1.2 Research Objectives

Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. Assess the role of NCDF in improving access rate in enhancing access to public secondary school education in Mombasa County.

- ii. Examine the role of NCDF in the provision of infrastructural facilities in enhancing access to public secondary school education in Mombasa County.
- iii. Assess the role of NCDF in the provision of instructional resources in enhancing access to public secondary school education in Mombasa County.

2.0 Conceptual Framework

This study was guided by the theory of socialist economics of education. This theory was propounded by a French writer and historian called Louis Blanc in 1848. The theory underscores the need to create an economy that redistributes income from the rich to the poor so as to create equality of well-being. The socialist economics theory forms the basis of the Lorenz curve, which is the geometric representation of the distribution of income among families in a given country, at a given time. The Lorenz curve measures the cumulative percentage of families from the poorest to the richest on the horizontal axis, while the cumulative percentage of income is put on the vertical axis. In the present study, the cumulative percentages are described in terms of quintiles. When quintiles are used, the population is divided into five equal portions.

As illustrated in figure 2.1 the investment of NCDF subsidy in the financing of secondary education consequently would yield to results such as improved access, transition and retention rates, and improved quality secondary education. The investment of NCDF in secondary education in Kenya mainly takes the form of bursaries for needy but bright students, improvement and construction of school facilities, textbooks among others. The independent variable is the role of NCDF as a financing model of secondary school education while the dependent variable is the enhanced results observable in the provision of quality secondary education as a result of investing NCDF in the former.

Independent Variable

Dependent Variable

Source: Researcher (2018)

Figure 2.1 Relationship between a role(s) of NCDF in enhancing access to secondary education.

3.0 Research Design

The current study adopted descriptive survey research design to collect data on the role of NCDF in enhancing access to public secondary school education in Mombasa County. Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) define

descriptive design as a process of collecting data, in order to answer questions concerning the current status of the subject in the study, therefore determine and reports the way things are. The study location was Mombasa County Kenya since the researcher noted CDF is one of the factors affecting education in the County. The present study targeted 32 public secondary schools, 32 principals, 32 BOM chairpersons and 582 teachers from the four Sub-Counties in Mombasa County namely Mvita, Kisauni, Likoni and Changamwe. In this regard, all the 32 principals, 32 BOM chairpersons and 582 teachers in the four Sub-Counties totaling to 646 people comprised the target population in this study.

For analytical analysis, the multiple linear regression model is specified as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \varepsilon$$

This is a multilinear regression model: where Y the dependent variable of tax compliance,

β_0 is the regression intercept, β_1 to β_3 the regression coefficients, X_1 is Improving Access Rate,

X_2 is Provision of Infrastructure Facilities X_3 is Provision of Instructional Resources, and e is the residual error of the regression

4.0 Findings and discussions

4.4.1 Improving Access Rate to Secondary Education

Assess the role of NCDF in improving access rate in public secondary schools in Mombasa County

Table 4.4 Improving Access Rate to Secondary Education

Statement	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
My school was established through funds provided by NCDF.	50	2.9400	1.21907
My school has benefitted greatly from the NCDF kitty for the last three years.	50	2.8200	1.04374
The money received from NCDF kitty for the last three years was sufficient.	50	2.0800	.77828
More than 50% of the students in the school benefitted from NCDF bursary fund.	50	2.7400	.87622
Bursaries from the NCDF only benefitted the needy and deserving students.	50	2.6600	1.08063
Enrolment of students in the school has increased tremendously as a result of NCDF funding.	50	3.0200	.91451
Transition and retention rate has improved greatly in the school as a result of NCDF fund.'	50	3.0200	.86873
Completion rate of the students in the school is very high as a result of NCDF fund/bursary.	50	2.9800	.84491
Majority of the students are sent home frequently due to failure to pay school fees.	50	2.6400	1.27391
Bursaries allocated to students from the NCDF kitty is enough to make student settle down in the school	50	1.7800	.91003

Source: Research data, (2018)

The study findings in table 4.4 revealed that NCDF has a role to play in enhancing access to public secondary school education in Mombasa County. Aspects of the role of NCDF in improving access rate in public secondary schools in Mombasa County included My school was established through funds provided by NCDF scoring a mean of 2.9400. It has benefitted greatly from the NCDF kitty for the last three years mean 2.8200. The money received from NCDF kitty was sufficient for school development to mean of 2.0800. More than 50% of the students in the school benefitted from NCDF bursary a mean of 2.7400. Bursaries from the NCDF only benefitted the needy and deserving students' mean of 2.6600. Enrolment of students in the school has increased tremendously as a result of NCDF funding mean of 3.0200. Transition and retention rate has improved greatly in the school as a result of NCDF fund mean 3.0200. Completion rate of the students in the school is very high as a result of NCDF fund / bursary mean 2.9800. Majority of the students are sent home frequently due to failure to pay school fees a mean of 2.6400 and Bursaries allocated to students from the NCDF kitty is enough to make students settle down in the school mean of 1.7800.

4.4.2 Provision of Infrastructural Facilities

These statements were used to examine the role of NCDF in the provision of infrastructural facilities in public secondary schools in Mombasa County.

Table: 4. 5 Provision of Infrastructural Facilities

Statement	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
In my school, there are projects funded by the NCDF fund.	50	3.3400	1.50658
The funds from NCDF kitty often are released promptly.	50	1.9800	.97917
There are adequate classrooms for students in the school as a result of NCDF fund	50	2.0400	.90260
The school has been receiving NCDF subsidy for the renovation of classrooms and other school facilities for the last 3 years	50	1.9800	.91451
Generally, the NCDF fund has improved the infrastructure of the school.	50	2.1400	1.01035
The funds allocated to the school for the construction of school projects from the NCDF kitty is sufficient.	50	1.8200	.87342

Source: Research data, (2018)

The study findings in table 4.5 revealed that NCDF has a role to play in enhancing access to public secondary school education in Mombasa County. Aspects of the role of NCDF in the provision of infrastructural facilities in public secondary schools in Mombasa County included in my school, there are projects funded by the NCDF fund scoring a mean of 3.3400. The funds from NCDF kitty often are released promptly mean of 1.9800. There are adequate classrooms for students in the school as a result of the NCDF fund mean of 2.0400. The school has been receiving NCDF subsidy for the renovation of classrooms and other school facilities for the last 3 years mean 1.9800. Generally, the NCDF fund has improved the infrastructure of the school scoring a mean of 2.1400 and the funds allocated to the school for the construction of school projects from the NCDF kitty is sufficient to mean of 1.8200.

4.4.3 Provision of Instructional Resources.

Assess the role of NCDF in the provision of instructional resources in public secondary schools in Mombasa County

Table 4.6: Provision of Instructional Resources.

Statement	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
How do you rate the degree of funding by the NCDF in your school?	50	2.1600	.84177
In your opinion, to what extent is the support for instructional resources by the NCDF fund in your school?	50	2.2600	.82833
To what extent has the teaching & learning resources funded by NCDF promoted the performance of the school for the last 3 years?	50	2.4200	.90554
To what level of degree is the scarcity for textbooks and other instructional resources in the school?	50	2.6200	.83029
How do you rate the level of corruption in your school when it comes to procurement of instructional resources from NCDF fund	50	1.9600	.96806
How do you rate the extent to which the school depends on NCDF fund for instructional resource	50	2.1000	1.09265

Source: Research data, (2018)

The study findings in table 4.6 revealed that NCDF has a role to play in enhancing access to public secondary school education in Mombasa County. Aspects of the role of NCDF in the provision of instructional resources in public secondary schools in Mombasa County included the question of rating the degree of funding by the NCDF in the school scoring a mean of 2.1600. The extent to the support for instructional resources by the NCDF fund in your school mean of 2.2600. The extent of teaching & learning resources funded by NCDF promoted the performance of the school for the last 3 years mean of 2.4200. The level of degree is the scarcity for textbooks and other instructional resources in the school 2.6200. Rating the level of corruption in your school when it comes to procurement of instructional resources from NCDF fund a mean of 1.9600 and rating the extent to which the school depends on NCDF fund for instructional resources scoring a mean of 2.1000.

4.5 Enhancing access to education

Table 4.7 Enhancing access to education

Statement	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Improved infrastructure due to NCDF fund has enhanced secondary school education.	50	2.0400	.90260
Retention rate has improved greatly in the school as a result of NCDF fund.	50	1.9800	.91451
Bursaries allocated to students from the NCDF kitty has enhanced secondary school education	50	2.1400	1.01035
Transition rate has improved greatly in the school as a result of NCDF fund	50	1.8200	.87342

Source: Research data, (2018)

The study findings in table 4.6 revealed that NCDF has a role to play in enhancing access to public secondary school education in Mombasa County. Aspects included improved infrastructure due to NCDF fund have enhanced secondary school education scoring a mean of 2.0400. Retention rate has improved greatly in the school as a result of the NCDF fund mean of 1.9800. Bursaries allocated to students from the NCDF kitty has enhanced secondary school education mean of 2.1400 and Transition rate has improved greatly in the school as a result of NCDF fund mean of 1.8200.

4.7 Regression analysis

Table 4. Regression model: Model Summary

Mode	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error of the Estimate
	.921 ^a	.849	.839	.29775

The model summary gives the total variability in the dependent variable explained by the model. This then indicates the percentage R-square is the proportion of the variation in the dependent variable (Enhancing access to education) that was explained by variations in independent variables. In this case, R-Square shows that 84.9% of the variation was explained. The dispersion of the dependent variable is measured by Standard error of the estimate.

COEFFICIENTS^A

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
(Constant)	-.484	.248		-1.954	.057
IAR	.191	.093	.135	2.054	.046
PIF	.864	.073	.851	11.803	.000
PIR	-.006	.079	-.005	-.077	.939

Key; IAR – Improving Access Rate, P.I.F – Provision of Infrastructure Facilities, P.I.R – Provision of Instructional Resources,

From the regression model in Table 4, the findings indicated that Improving Access Rate had (At 95% confidence level, $P=0.05$) a $P\text{-Value}=0.046$, a value less than the significance level of 0.05. This shows a strong relationship between Improving Access Rate as a factor Enhancing Access of Education in secondary school. Secondly, the Provision of Infrastructure Facilities had a $P\text{-Value}=0.000$, connoting a strong relationship between the Provision of Infrastructure Facilities and Enhancing Access of Education in secondary school. Finally, Provision of Instructional Resources as a factor Enhancing Access of Education in secondary school scored a $P\text{-Value}=0.939$, which however indicated a weak relationship between Provision of Instructional Resources and Enhancing Access of Education in secondary school. This is generally a clear indication that on average three factors IAR – Improving Access Rate, P.I.F – Provision of Infrastructure Facilities, P.I.R – Provision of Instructional Resources strongly enhances access to education in public secondary school education in Mombasa County.

The regression model in Table above also revealed that holding all the three factors, (IAR – Improving Access Rate, P.I.F – Provision of Infrastructure Facilities, P.I.R – Provision of Instructional Resources) constant, access to education in public secondary school education in Mombasa County would be achieved at the unit of -0.484. A unit increase in IAR – Improving Access Rate would cause an increase in access to education in public secondary school education in Mombasa County by a factor of 0.191, a unit increase in P.I.F – Provision of Infrastructure Facilities by a factor of 0.864 and a unit increase in P.I.R – Provision of Instructional Resources would cause a decrease in access to education in public secondary school education in Mombasa County by a factor of -0.006.

5.0 Conclusions and recommendations

The first objective of this research study was to assess the role of NCDF in improving access rate in public secondary schools in Mombasa County. From the result, the study found that NCDF has a role to play in enhancing access to public secondary school education in Mombasa County. This research study found that schools in Mombasa County were established through funds provided by NCDF and that these schools have benefitted greatly from the NCDF kitty for the last three years. The second objective of this research study was to examine the role of NCDF in the provision of infrastructural facilities in public secondary schools in Mombasa County. From the results, the study concluded that NCDF has a role to play in enhancing access to public secondary school education in Mombasa County. The third objective of this research study was to assess the role of NCDF in the provision of instructional resources in public secondary schools in Mombasa County. From the result, the study concluded that NCDF has a role to play in enhancing access to public secondary school education in Mombasa County. In summary, this study research concluded that NCDF has a role in enhancing access to public secondary school education in Mombasa County.

The study recommends that: as much as possible CDF bursary awarded to students should be adequate to sustain the students in schools and improve their survival rates. This, in turn, will motivate primary school graduates to join secondary school. The funds should be dispatched in time to enable schools to provide the necessary resources to attract more students to schools. The bursaries should also be awarded in time so as to enable students to be within the school gates and not spend valuable time chasing after the money. School administrators should also be patient and not send away students who may not have completed paying fees but are beneficiaries of the fund. The government should increase the amount of CDF dispatched to schools for improvement and growth of school infrastructure so as to enhance access to secondary education.